

Management Functions in PAUD (Early Children Education)

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ABSTRACT: This article aims to find out how kindergarten management is managed properly, the application of POAK (planning, organizing, actuating, controlling) functions in PAUD. The literature review is from previous research. This article uses the search and review method, where the review process begins with a search engine, Google Scholar, to search for articles with keywords. The author finds the scope of the articles reviewed is still very limited so that it needs to be followed up related to kindergarten management research. The results of the review show that the creativity of teachers in kindergarten can be realized optimally if they apply good management. Research on this topic is very limited so that further research is needed on the management function for teacher creativity in kindergartens in general. The theoretical benefit of this article is to know the management function for in kindergarten.

KEYWORDS: Management Function; PAUD

1. INTRODUCTION

Background of this Article

Management is an activity to manage an organization to achieve its goals. In realizing organizational goals, management emphasizes the use of resources effectively and efficiently. Effectiveness is related to carrying out a job with correct procedures to achieve goals. So, management is a discipline related to government, managing something so that it becomes good and in accordance with the direction of goals and principles of regular implementation. (Nuryadika & Hariri, 2021)

Management activities are activities that reflect the existence of a system, which consists of several aspects or supporting factors

Education management in Indonesia is a central point in realizing the goals of Human Resources (HR) development. In his observation, education management in Indonesia still has not shown the desired professional ability. The problem of education management is one of the main problems that causes a crisis in the world of education in Indonesia. (Iisnawati, 2017)

Educational management is the whole "process" of making appropriate personnel and material resources available and effective for the attainment of common goals. It performs functions by influencing the actions of people. This process includes planning, organization, coordination, supervision, implementation and service of everything regarding school affairs that are directly related to school education such as curriculum, teachers, students, methods, learning tools and guidance. Also questions regarding land and school buildings, equipment, supplies and financing needed for the implementation of education (Khusniyah, 2021)

Talking about management, management can be carried out by any organization in various fields, including schools. School management is a process and institution that leads and guides the implementation of school assignments as an organization and realizes the goals and objectives of school education that have been set (Ardiansyah et al, 2021). In schools its success involves key stakeholders such as teachers, students, parents (Lina Fikriyah, 2017)

Management in her successful school involves key stakeholders such as teachers, students, parents. 7

The word management is translated into English manager which means to handle. Which, when translated into Indonesian, means management and processing. According to Usman (2009: 5), the essence of management is seen as a process function and as a task. The focus of school management is to function and optimize the ability to develop school plans so that schools can run synergistically. Hasibuan (2006:2) further explained that management is the science and art of managing the process of utilizing human resources and other resources effectively and efficiently to achieve certain goals. Management is a science and an art, in which management explains the rules, causal relationships and all of them are dynamic based on previous knowledge and continue to develop according to the demands of the times. The art that is meant is the knowledge that will be achieved is obtained from the skills of a person who is obtained from experience and observation.

Management function

In general, there are four management functions that people often call POAC, namely planning, organizing, actuating, and controlling. The first two functions are categorized as mental, while the next two are categorized as physical activities. A management can be said to be successful if the four functions above can be carried out properly. Weaknesses in one of the management functions will affect the overall management and result in not achieving an effective and efficient process efficient.

1. planning

Planning is an initial step in an activity, Usman (2009:65) says that planning is a number of predetermined activities to be carried out in a certain period in order to achieve the goals set. In order to carry out a plan for early childhood education, planning aspects include the process of implementing early childhood education which includes the process of accepting new students, activities and places to carry out these activities.

2. organizing (organizing)

Organizing is uniting resources in optimizing the ability of each individual to realize cooperation in achieving goals. Rivai and Pure (2009: 103), educational organization is aimed at bringing together all components of education in a synergistic organization to be able to provide good education.

3. implementation (acting)

The concept of management in early childhood education is the implementation of activities in moving people from various resources in an organization. For the smooth process of implementing this activity, a leader is needed who can motivate his subordinates through an effective and persuasive communication approach, in order to encourage subordinates to carry out program activities according to their functions and responsibilities. PAUD as an educational organization adheres to the principles and concepts of actuating in running the organization to improve organizational performance. A leader must be able to play a leadership role to be able to recruit his subordinates and various PAUD organizational resources.

4. supervision (controlling)

Supervision is one of the management functions that is oriented to control (supervise), supervision in an organization plays an important role in achieving organizational goals. Rivai and pure (2009:104) "controlling education is intended to ensure that the implementation of education is carried out as planned and all components of education are driven synergistically to achieve educational goals. (Ulfa 2015)

Importance and Gap of Research

There are many theories about the management function, in this study the author focuses on the management function. The idea of this management function can be applied as management in early childhood education.

So through this review journal I will dig deeper into the management function so as to increase knowledge in how to apply the management function for early childhood education.

The development of the theory of management in schools, because so far management has focused a lot on elementary, junior high, high school, university schools. Therefore I am very interested in conducting research on the benefits of management in Early Childhood Education. As well as from several articles that I found in other countries management functions in PAUD but the goals are different. This article covers Indonesia, Australia, Africa, Malaysia, and Turkey.

Previous Research on management

Planning Indicators in the Management of Leading Early Childhood Education Institutions Upik Elok Endang Rasmayani¹, Warananingtyas Palupi², Jumi atmoko³, Nurul Shofiatin Zuhro⁴, Anjar Fitrianingtyas⁵ Early Childhood Education Teacher Education, Sebelas Maret University

This study focuses on extracting data on the management planning of the Superior PAUD in Surakarta. This study uses a descriptive qualitative approach. Data were obtained by observation and interviews using Google Form with resource persons consisting of principals, playgroup class teachers, group A class teachers, class B teachers, dance extracurricular teachers, English teachers, and drawing extracurricular teachers. This study reveals that curriculum management planning, which consists of 7 (seven) main indicators, is the earliest component set by the Superior PAUD institution. The determination of the indicators of curriculum management planning has implications for human resource management planning, infrastructure, financing, and management cooperation.

TEACHER PERFORMANCE IMPROVEMENT MANAGEMENT Ahmad Zubair (MAN, South Bengkulu Regency) (MAP FKIP Unib Study Program) Aliman (MAP FKIP Unib Study Program)

The general purpose of this study is to describe the management of teacher performance improvement. The specific objectives are to describe: 1) planning for improving teacher performance, 2) managing teacher performance improvement, 3) monitoring and evaluating teacher performance improvement management and 4) problems found in managing teacher performance improvement. This research method is descriptive qualitative and data collection techniques are interviews, observations, and documentation. The research subjects were principals and teachers. The results showed that the planning, monitoring and evaluation of the management of teacher performance improvement were effective. However, based on the implementation of the management of improving teacher performance, several problems were found, namely external problems and internal problems

FUNCTIONS OF PRINCIPAL MANAGEMENT, MOTIVATION, AND TEACHER PERFORMANCE

Rita Lisnawati Education Management Study Program, State University of Surabaya

This study aims to determine how the level of principal management functions, teacher motivation, and teacher performance and how much influence teacher motivation has on teacher performance. Data collection techniques used questionnaires (questionnaires) distributed to respondents, observations, interviews, and documentation. Responses measured through questionnaires were adjusted to 4 Likert scales. Validity test using Pearson Product Moment. The analytical technique used to answer research questions uses descriptive statistical analysis, while to answer research hypotheses related to teacher motivation and teacher performance using Simple Linear Regression Inferential Analysis. The results showed that

1) The level of the principal's management function is in the high category with an average score.

IMPLEMENTATION ANALYSIS OF EDUCATION MANAGEMENT FUNCTIONS IN SD LUQMAN AL HAKIM NGAWI

This study aims to analyze and describe the management of educational institutions in SD Luqman Al Hakim Ngawi Ngawi. Management analysis includes: 1) Curriculum and Learning Management, 2) Student Management, 3) Educator and Education Personnel Management, 4) Facilities and Infrastructure Management, 5) Education Financing Management, 6) Public Relations Management, 7) Education Supervision Management. Data collection techniques were carried out by surveys, observations, and interviews with school principals and teachers. The data analysis technique used a qualitative descriptive technique. The results of the study indicate that SD Luqman Al Hakim Ngawi Ngawi implements good management of educational institutions and that management has been carried out to support school quality improvement.

Recognition and Behavior Management of Gifted and Gifted Students in an Educational Environment Inclusivey

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Keywords: inclusive education, primary school students, student introduction, elementary school teachers, behavior management
During student development, enrichment of academic and psychosocial activities according to the different educational needs of students is important.

This study aims to identify the opinions of primary school teachers in Turkey, Czech Republic, Italy, and Germany. Teachers' opinions were investigated and compared about the skills, interests, intelligence, and individual abilities of students in an inclusive education environment with gifted and gifted students. In addition, the methods, techniques and strategies they employ in behavior management, development and student bonding with each other are analyzed. This research is a qualitative descriptive study. Layered sampling was used from the objective sampling method. The study group consisted of 248 elementary school teachers. In data analysis used content analysis. To ensure the validity and reliability of the study, coder reliability coefficient, expert opinion, confirmability strategy techniques were used. In the Czech Republic, Turkey and Italy, the dimensions of teaching to determine students' interests, abilities and intelligence were emphasized, while the German dimensions of cooperation with parents and stakeholders were highlighted. Teachers who participate in the development of positive behavior prioritize the communication process, stimulate educational activities in the management of unwanted behavior and bond students with one another. Responses based on the effectiveness of teacher education in relation to the management of students' interests, skills and intelligence, development and behavior revealed that teachers were unable to decipher appropriate approaches to different problem areas. It was observed that there were not enough applications to contribute to the psychosocial development of students with different developmental characteristics. Osman Sabancı entitled "Strategies for Teachers of Gifted and Gifted Students " was accepted within

the framework of the EU Turkey Erasmus + Mixed School Education programme. Furthermore, the research was also presented as an oral presentation at Gazi University between 4-6 May 2017 at the International Conference on Gifted Students: New educational approaches and applications in the context of students' interest in an inclusive educational environment., educational abilities and practices aimed at identifying and developing their intelligence. Gazi University, Gazi School of Education, Ankara, Turkey.

PAUD teachers' management of their changing role regarding digital technology in kindergarten: A grounded theory study Vicki Schriever Setting the research context Early childhood education and care in Australia has undergone unprecedented changes. The studies reported in this paper have been influenced by the Australian policy context, including the consistent implementation of national policies.

This paper examines how early childhood teachers employed in kindergartens understand and manage their changing roles with regard to digital technology. Nineteen participants were involved in this study. Early childhood teacher, digital technology, kindergarten, professional agency, professional identity, pedagogical practice, family relations Keywords Symbolic interactionism provides a theoretical lens to investigate the life experiences of each early childhood teacher and grounded theory provides methodological theories and methods. After data analysis, a central category, Professional Bodies, and three main categories, Professional Identity, Pedagogical Practice, and Relationships with Families, were derived. These categories, together with the relevant empirical literature, form the main features of the Early Childhood Teacher Management Digital Technology Framework. This framework contributes to knowledge and presents a substantive theory that explains how PAUD teachers manage their changing roles with digital technology in their kindergartens.

MALAYSIA ONLINE JOURNAL OF EDUCATION MANAGEMENT (MOJEM) FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT SKILLS BETWEEN TK TEACHERS IN SELANGOR

Husaina Banu Kenayathulla(PhD) & Juliana Jupri

Although financial management is one of the most important skills in life, its importance is still not recognized by society due to lack of exposure. Several studies address this issue. This study aims to identify financial management skills in kindergarten teachers in Selangor. This study involved 60 teachers from selected kindergartens in Selangor.

Keywords: financial literacy, financial management, Kindergarten, University Malaya, MALAYSIA This was conducted to determine the level of financial literacy and financial management skills of kindergarten teachers. This study used a quantitative methodology and the data were analyzed by descriptive method. The results of this study indicate that kindergarten teachers have a high level of financial literacy and financial management skills, especially in basic financial concepts related to spending and saving. The results also show that there are differences in the level of financial management skills of urban and rural kindergarten teachers, especially in the aspect of credit management.

Based on the information above, it shows that research on management has been widely carried out in various countries, management is very important to be implemented depending on the success or failure of an institution, PAUD management in Indonesia is mostly focused on achieving the success of PAUD output, in contrast to the existing management. in other countries the management studied in PAUD is very much different from Indonesia. Management in Indonesia is very important, unlike other countries, it is more management that is not implemented in Indonesia, from the literature it shows that PAUD management is very important both in Indonesia and in other countries but different management is applied and is much different. her success.

Research Questions this Article

Therefore, this article examines the management function in early childhood education in kindergarten. This objective is answered by the research questions below.

How can the management function be implemented in PAUD?

2. METHODS

This literature review focuses on the management function in PAUD teachers. An integrative review methodology was used to allow entry of various theoretical and empirical literatures. The review process was taken from the relevant literature using a transparent and reproducible search method, and the data obtained were analyzed and synthesized. The review process starts with the google scholar search engine, to search for articles with the keywords: "management function to improve" creativity PAUD teacher". The search ranged from 2018 – 2022 and identified 2018 totals 11746, 2021 totals 2801, 2022 totals 149.

Storage and Exclusion Criteria

1. Type

The research design used in this scientific research is qualitative

2. Type of Intervention

Type of Intervention

The main study in scientific research is the management function based on management theory. Journals that match the criteria for the management function will be studied further. The criteria for the journals selected for review are journals with the theme of management in PAUD and other formal school levels. The inclusion criteria for this article are shown in Table 1:

Table 1. Criteria for Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion
1. leading early childhood education institution planning	1. recognition and behavioral management of gifted students in an inclusive educational environment
2. teacher performance improvement management	2. analysis of the implementation of education management functions in schools base
3. principal management functions, motivation, and teacher performance.	3. financial management skills between kindergarten, teacher
4. PAUD teacher management on their changing roles related to digital technology in kindergarten analysis of the implementation of management functions education	4. Manager and Teacher Opinion Analysis about School Risk Management in the Internal Control Risk Management Model Framework
5. analysis of the implementation of education management functions	5. Financial management skills among kindergarten teachers at
6. Teacher performance improvement management	6. Opinion Analysis of Managers and Teachers on School Risk Management in the Control Risk Management Model Framework Internal
7. Planning Indicators in the Management of Early Childhood Education Institutions Superior	7. Examination of Teacher Opinions About Use of Management Tactics Impression
8. early childhood education management at PAUD BINTANG Rabbani Pekanbaru	8. Participatory Management, Professional Development, and Teacher Work Achievement in Public High Schools in Country Ogun Section, Nigeria
9. Management of Character Education in Kindergarten	9. How school management prevents private sector training

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. RESULTS

This section reports the results of the articles reviewed. The results of the analysis show that most of the articles focus on education above kindergarten. However, most of the article reviews have not discussed much about management in kindergarten. Most of the review articles only discuss management at the top level schools, while the review of articles at the PAUD level is still limited and not many. However, based on the results of the review that I found in the review article, there is a significant relationship between the management function and school success. The results of research studies representing journals from various countries can be seen in the following table:

Table 2. Results of Literature Review

No	Title	Author (s) and Year	Type of Organization	N	County	Method	Result
1	FUNCTIONS PRINCIPAL MANAGEMENT, MOTIVATION, TEACHER PERFORMANCE	OF Rita Lisnawati Education Management Study Program of Surabaya (2021)	Elementary School	208 response	Indonesian DOI: http://dx.doi.org/10.26740/jp.v2n2.p143-149	qualitative descriptive	to find out how the level of principal management functions, teacher motivation, and teacher performance and how much influence teacher motivation has on teacher performance.
2	ANALYSIS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF EDUCATION MANAGEMENT FUNCTIONS IN SD LUQMAN AL HAKIM NGAWI:	Tri Wardati Khusniyah School Teacher Education Base, STKIP Modern Ngawi (2021)	Elementary School	208 response	ISSN : 2615-5710 Vol. IV No. 1	qualitative descriptive	Management analysis, implementing good management of educational institutions and that management has been carried out to support the improvement of school quality.
3	Management enhancement teacher performance	Ahmad Zubair (MAN Regency. Bengkulu South), Vine Nur Sasongko (Prodi FOLDER FKIP Unib Aliman (Prodi FOLDER FKIP Unib (2017)	MTS	50 KS, GURU	Indonesia ISSN: 1979-732X	Descriptive qualitative	planning, monitoring and evaluation based on implementation management performance improvement teacher found some problems that is problem external and internal problems.
4	Indicator Planning on Management Institution Children's Education Early Age Superior	Wilson Beautiful Endang Rasmayani, Warrantin gtyas	PAUD	11 KS, Teacher	Indonesia DOI: 10.31004/obsession.v5i1,591	Descriptive qualitative	planning management the curriculum that consists of 7 (seven) main indicator, is components that

		Palupi2, Fridaymok o3, Nurul Shofiati(20 21)					the first determined by PAUD lembaga Superior. Indicator setting Planning management this curriculum implications for planning source management human resources, infrastructure, financing and cooperation.
5	Confession management student behavior talented Environment Education Inclusivey	and Osman Sabanci, safiy in sarycy fur(2018)	PAUD	248 teacher	Ankara, turkey	Descriptive e qualitative	. teacher who participate In development positive behavior prioritize communication process, stimulate activity education in management behavior that is not wanted and student bond one each other.
6	Management teacher top PAUD role change They are related digital technology in the garden child: A study grounded(2020) theory	Vicki Schriever University sunshine coasts, Australia grounded(2020)	PAUD	19 respond en	Australia DOI: 10.1177/1 83693912 0979065 journals.s agepub.co	qualitative	contribute to knowledge and presenting theory the substantive Explain how is teacher PAUD manage role change they With digital technology in kindergarten- their child.
7	SKILLS AN MANAGEMENT FINANCE BETWEEN TEACHER SELANGOR	Husaina Banu Kenayathul la(PhD) & Juliana TK IN Jupri(2016)	PAUD (TK itanagor)	60 teacher	Malaysia	Qualitative &data analysis	Kindergarten teachers have literacy level finance and Skills Management financial especially high on the basic concept Financial concerning expenditure and savings. risk analysis school is in
8	Opinion Analysis manager	Merfaruk and AK2	ADM& high teacher	22 schoolparticipant	turkey	qualitative	

	Teacher about Management School Risk in Skeleton Model Management Risk Control internal	governor an NYYDE, Turkey SevilleAHy N3, University Gaziantep, Turkey(2021)					between steps-possible steps uncertainty and opportunity for time front. Condition the most important to make the right one is taken against risk with high scores, teacher uses
9	Pen Check got teacher About Use Tactics Management Impression	Fatih BOZBAYI NDIR 2020	13 TEACHER	SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL	Turkey	Qualitative	different tactics for produce the impression that wanted on other people with use different tactics depending on cases and individuals
							DOI: http://dx.doi.org/10.30831/akueg.567225
10	EDUCATION MANAGEMENT AGE CHILDREN EARLY AT PAUD STAR RABBANI PEKANBARU	Suharni, 2019	managers, educators, students and people old	PAUD	Indonesia	descriptive qualitative	The management function places great emphasis on cooperation based on sincerity, enthusiasm, and dedication high loyalty. Planning is done by strategic planning, preparation of learning plans
11	Management participatory, Development Profession, and teacher Job Performance in Public High Schools in Ogun State, Nigeria		504 participants	SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL	Okaka, ni happy	Analysis data	teacher performance significant and positively related with development professional and participatory management. This study concludes that teacher performance can be improved through two management intervention strategies

12	Management Education Characters Kindergarten	Sobarna, A., & inJudge, A. (2017).	Amount garden child right	kindergart en Indonesia DOI 10.15294/ ijeces.v6i 2.20188	Qualitative Study case	pilot project kindergarten already implemented in an integrated manner character building in learning through development habituation and specialized in development learning. theme.
13	How management school prevent private training	Neeta Srivastava Research scholars, Faculty of Business administrator ion, Himalayan university, itanagar, AP(2021)	whole institution India. of	Itanagar Survey two: 10.17051/ ilkonline. 2021.01.4 18	Least Squares (PLS)	People who more educated less dependent on help public, and with so less susceptible to slump economy. Public based on more knowledge capable face current challenge and future

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